

VOLUME-1, ISSUE-11

ANALYSIS OF POEMS

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named after Mirzo Ulugbek

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ANNOTATION: This article gives information about analysis of poems. In this article it has several paragraphs, which give full data about this. Stylistic analysis in literary studies often involves interpreting the layers of a text through close reading rather than through plot. It takes inner thoughts and reveals them with logical descriptions such as point of view, setting, images, symbols, tone, atmosphere, personification. In this article, candidates can learn how to be a good learner and what is analysis of poems. And candidates can learn how to use it?

KEY WORDS: Rhyme, meter, metaphor, dramatic language, monologue, conflict, tension, soliloquy, simile, personification, poetic language .

Analysis means literally picking a poem apart--looking at elements such as imagery, metaphor, poetic language, rhyme scheme, and so on--in order to see how they all work together to produce the poem's meaning. By looking at a poem in terms of its elements, one decodes the poem.

What is stylistic analysis of poem?

Stylistic analysis in literary studies generally assumes to explain the layers of text by close reading than relying on the plot. It accomplishes internal thoughts and unfolds them with a logistic description such as point of view, setting, imagery, symbolism, tone, atmosphere, personification etc.

What type of stylistic devices are used in a poem?

Rhyme, meter, alliteration, caesura, simile, metaphor, irony, and allusion are some of the most common poetic devices. Caesuras, in particular, have the powerful effect of forcing readers to pause dramatically and perhaps reevaluate their thought processes.

What is rhythm in stylistics?

Rhythm Definition

Rhythm (RIH-thum) is the recurring pattern of stressed and unstressed syllables in the flow of language in a literary work, particularly verse. Rhythm is best understood

as the pace and beat of a poem, and it's created through specific variations of syllabic emphasis.

What is a type of figurative language?

Figurative language is an excellent tool you can use in writing that helps your audience better visualize and understand your message. There are several different types including: Similes. Metaphors. Idioms. Poetic language is usually created through alliteration, metaphor, simile, and other techniques that appeal to readers' emotions and senses.

Metaphor is a common poetic device where an object in, or the subject of, a poem is described as being the same as another otherwise unrelated object. Metaphors, also known as direct comparisons, are one of the most common literary devices. A metaphor is a statement in which two objects, often unrelated, are compared to each other. Example of metaphor: This tree is the god of the forest. Obviously, the tree is not a god—it is, in fact, a tree. With metaphor, the qualities of one thing are figuratively carried over to another. When I say, “Dude, I'm drowning in work,” I'm using qualities associated with one thing—the urgency and helplessness of drowning—to convey meaning for another thing—the work I've got to do. Metaphors are everywhere: He's a couch potato.

Simile is common poetic device. The subject of the poem is described by comparing it to another object or subject, using 'as' or 'like'. For example, the subject may be 'creeping as quietly as a mouse' or be 'sly, like a fox'. For example: as proud as a peacock, as busy as a bee and so on. A simile is a direct comparison of two like or unlike things. A simile helps your reader or listener visualise, understand and have a better conception of the quality of the nouns being compared.

Personification is a poetic device where animals, plants or even inanimate objects, are given human qualities – resulting in a poem full of imagery and description. Personification is a poetic device where animals, plants or even inanimate objects, are given human qualities – resulting in a poem full of imagery and description.

A figure of speech composed of a striking exaggeration. For example, see James Tate's lines “She scorched you with her radiance” or “He was more wronged than Job.” Hyperbole usually carries the force of strong emotion, as in Andrew Marvell's description of a forlorn lover: The sea him lent those bitter tears.

What is dramatic language?

Dramatic language is language traditionally associated with drama. It incorporates theatrical vocabulary, designed to pack an emotional punch, and elicit strong feelings. Traditionally, it does so by mimicking these strong feelings, and

presenting them in a hyperbolic fashion. Dramatic language is often associated with emotive interjections - picture a Shakespearean character on stage, lamenting loudly and peppering their speech with lots of 'oh!'s and 'ah!'s.

A monologue is a long speech delivered to other characters. A soliloquy is a long speech where a character talks to himself/herself or voices his/her thoughts aloud for the benefit of the audience. A monologue is used to show a character's thoughts and motivations. A monologue is given when a character is speaking to another character, while a former speech or soliloquy is not. Monologues help reveal something about a character. They are similar to stories because they have a distinct beginning, middle, and end. Poetic form. dramatic monologue, a poem written in the form of a speech of an individual character; it compresses into a single vivid scene a narrative sense of the speaker's history and psychological insight into his character.

A soliloquy is a monologue in which a character in a play expresses thoughts and feelings while being alone on stage. Soliloquies allow dramatists to communicate information about a character's state of mind, hopes, and intentions directly to an audience. In terms of the interrelationship between the soliloquist and his known or unknown addressees, the soliloquy may be divided into four basic types: Plain Soliloquy, Attended Soliloquy, Soliloquy with Props, and Dialogical Soliloquy.

What is conflict and tension?

What Are the Differences Between Conflict and Tension? While tension simmers under the surface, conflict is generally out in the open—it's tension realized. Tension might be present an unspoken rivalry between the protagonist and antagonist or in the audience's awareness of an impending disaster.

What is tension in literature?

Tension happens as your reader anticipates conflict (that thing that is stopping your character getting what they really want) impacting the thing your protagonist desires the most. Suspense grows steadily throughout the course of a novel while the conflict remains unresolved.

What is a conflict in a poem?

In literature, a conflict is a literary device characterized by a struggle between two opposing forces. Conflict provides crucial tension in any story and is used to drive the narrative forward. More precisely, conflict means thwarted, endangered, or opposing desire. It's basically when a character wants something but something else gets in the way. Maybe the character wants a thing but can't get it. Maybe the character has something but is in danger of losing it.

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